

SATISFACTORY QUALITY SCENE RELATIONSHIP MANAGEMENT BY SCHEMATIZED STRUCTURE

Dr. Nasser Fegh-hi Farahmand ^{*1}, Shirin Pour Haji Ali Farid ²

^{*1} Department of Management, Tabriz Branch, Islamic Azad University, Tabriz, IRAN

² East Azerbaijan Behzisti Organization, Tabriz, IRAN

Abstract:

The role of organizations is to implement strategy. A fundamental proposition in strategy is that distribution methods must be aligned with customers and competitive advantage. Unfortunately, method successful measurement literature has provided ambiguous guidance to managers. This paper proposes a relation of organizational relationship management by schematized structure and reviews the satisfactory quality scene strategies and performance measurement literature to develop a conceptual model and research propositions. In fact, organizations influence whether or not those organizations engage in satisfactory quality scene strategies. In this field, the focus is on the special characteristics of schematized structure such as education type and level. The facilitator manager's characteristics showing a significant association with a commitment to organizational relationship management and also organizational relationship management showed a positive association with those schematized structure with a growth orientation. It is concluded that facilitator manager's characteristics can be important in explaining and compilation the organizational relationship management within the organizations for implementation. This paper is to explore the ways in which certain characteristics of schematized structure of organizations generate a tendency to prepare formal written satisfactory quality scene strategies.

Keywords:

Organizational relationship management, schematized structure, satisfactory quality scene strategies, satisfactory quality scene relationship management.

Cite This Article: Dr. Nasser Fegh-hi Farahman, and Shirin Pour Haji Ali Farid, “Satisfactory Quality Scene Relationship Management by Schematized Structure.” *International Journal of Research – Granthaalayah*, Vol. 3, No. 4(2015): 56-69.

1. INTRODUCTION

A positive experience throughout the customer's cycle should foster trust and develop loyalty, therefore allowing organizations to generate more revenue for less incremental expenditure as:

- 1) Making new customers aware of a product or service with loyal customers tend to receive more frequently and happy existing customers are more willing to receive other services from organization and try new service offerings.
- 2) The cost of servicing existing customers can be lower by security of future revenues, which is much higher with happy customers.

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL of RESEARCH –GRANTHAALAYAH

A knowledge Repository

For strategic purposes, satisfy of an intangible asset in its own right is not particularly relevant; however, an understanding of how this satisfy is comprised and the key metrics that impact on the assets' contribution to organization successful can be extremely beneficial for management decision making. Recent research into strategy implementation is damning in its findings. The organizations field is now giving high priority to developing metrics.

The strategy implementation, strategic control, satisfactory quality scene and successful measurement literature develop a conceptual model and research propositions. In fact, without organizational customers organizations would not exist. The strategic importance of organizational customers is discussed as an asset. Also this paper describes the approach to organizational relationship management at organizations.

The role of organizations is to implement strategy. A fundamental proposition in strategy is that distribution methods must be aligned with customers and competitive advantage. Unfortunately, method successful measurement literature has provided ambiguous guidance to managers.

In order to achieve satisfactory quality scene success, it is important to understand the relationship between method successful measures and strategy implementation success. It is also important to know whether, regardless of strategy, the same method successful measures should be used.

The key question in terms of ensuring that method strategy supports satisfactory quality scene successful is how do we know our method strategy is performing? In order to understand whether the method is performing or not, we need to ensure that the method measures are appropriate for each satisfactory quality scene strategy. Although organizational relationship management has been one of the fastest growing organizations, critics point to the high failure rate of the organizational relationship management projects as evidenced by organizations studies. The purpose of the study is to investigate success and failures of organizational relationship management system implementations. Also this study found that the scope, size, complexity and duration of the organizational relationship management projects seem to vary quite significantly across organizations. Poor planning, lack of clear objectives and not recognizing the need for organization change are the key reasons for organizational relationship management failures. The satisfactory quality scene field is now giving high priority to developing satisfactory quality scene metrics. The role of satisfactory quality scene is to implement satisfactory quality scene strategy. Effective organizational relationship management is one of the important factors in organizations success. There is schematized structure who argues that formal written planning may be inappropriate for the organizations but this seems a minority view. It can be argued that organizational relationship management is as important to organizations as to larger organizations and standard textbooks on entrepreneurship offer chapters on satisfactory quality scene plan whilst a range of specialist publications outline the best ways of writing satisfactory quality scene plan (Sahlman, 1997, 67; Monks, 2001, 41; Naffziger, et al, 1991, 21). A fundamental proposition in satisfactory quality scene strategy is that satisfactory quality scene plan must be aligned with customers and competitive advantage.

Unfortunately, satisfactory quality scene plan performance measurement literature has provided ambiguous guidance to satisfactory quality scene managers. In organizations, where a satisfactory quality scene strategy exists, the preparation of the organizational relationship management may have been driven by external forces. The most obvious of these are the requirements of external agencies providing funding for either start up or expansion. However, the satisfactory quality scene strategies may serve as a strategic planning document for the managers, entrepreneurs and educated workers, a plan to guide the satisfactory quality scene and serve as a basis for taking strategic decisions and also it may serve as a subsequent monitoring device (Deakins, 2003, 329; Fegh-hi farahmand, 2005, 118). In view of its perceived ongoing value to the small business it might be expected that organizational relationship management would be a feature of many, if not most, organizations. In order to achieve satisfactory quality scene success, it is important to understand the relationship between Organizational relationship management by Educated Managers and strategy deployment success. As management itself becomes more emphatically fast-paced and intuitive, in order to deal with complexity and unpredictability, research is beginning to accumulate showing that coaching formats used in management support are more effective than training in the older logical comprehensive pursuits.

2. SATISFACTORY QUALITY SCENE STRATEGIES

The satisfactory quality scene relationship model suggests strategy is a more important influence on method measures than variables such as satisfactory quality scene relationship characteristics, stage of service lifecycle, market share, organizational or strategic organization unit size, profitability and growth, environment or competitors.

Strategy 1) Satisfactory quality scene Pull vs Satisfactory quality scene Push: Traditional successful measurement systems were profitable focused and were neither multidimensional nor strategic. Based on the degree of service innovation inherent in strategies, it is likely that they would compete with higher quality services and be first to market with new generation services. Conversely, pull strategy would depend more on efficiency and cost reduction to compete and rely more on older generation services. As a result, pull would place greater emphasis on cost control measures in supporting strategy. pull measures of managers may be more important than pull measures of successful.

Strategy 2) frequent satisfactory quality scene vs infrequent satisfactory quality scene: Control by successful large pull involved frequent successful reporting. Pull satisfactory quality scene would be expected to be similar to cost leaders as they operate in relatively certain environments with existing service receivers and undertake little service innovation. As a result, the measures they use could be frequent yet still be meaningful.

Strategy 3) Social satisfactory quality scene vs Economic satisfactory quality scene: satisfactory quality scene relationship management were outcome focused and neither multidimensional nor strategic. The control method of successful pull included careful output monitoring and was expected to be associated with pull.

Strategy 4) Satisfactory quality scene quality / qualitative vs Satisfactory quality scene cost / quantitative: Based on the degree of service innovation inherent in pull strategies, it is likely that they would compete with higher quality services and be first to market with new generation services. Conversely, pull would depend more on efficiency and cost reduction to compete and rely more on older generation services. As a result, pull would place greater emphasis on cost control measures in supporting organizations strategy.

Strategy 5) Environmental satisfactory quality scene vs Organizational satisfactory quality scene: As pull target new markets, it appears appropriate they emphasis environmental measures. Conversely, pull would rely more on organizational and need to monitor internal efficiency while they compete with older generation services.

Strategy 6) Strategically satisfactory quality scene vs Operational satisfactory quality scene: Successful measures must be aligned with organization strategy. The optimum control system required two different approaches operating at different hierarchal levels.

The literature argues shows that the extent to which each determinant of performance impacts firm performance is a function of the performance metrics. Further, define performance as the sum of all processes that will lead managers to taking appropriate actions in the present that will create a performing organization in the future or in other words, doing today what will lead to measured value outcomes tomorrow. Schematized structure' recent research reviewing corporate coaching programs that we can see this move from intuition towards rationalized models as complementary and off-setting to developments in strategic management (Mintzberg, 1994, 89; Mintzberg, et al, 1998, 45; Schwenk, et al, 1993, 17). Like all scientific enterprises, a period of accumulation of evidence will be required before definitive conclusions may be drawn (Brown, et al, 1998, 88; Deakin, et al 2003, 64; Mason, et al, 2004, 3). However, there are early gleanings that evidence based evaluation research is underway. For this reason by coupling quality with customer service recovering satisfaction as Figure 1, a few tactical actions for implementation (Mason and Stark, 2004, 205; Peters, 1988, 160) can make the challenge simpler and provide leadership (Minnow, 1996, 5; Fegh-hi farahmand, 2009; Rue & et al, 1998, 97).

Fig 1: satisfactory quality scene strategies model

Anyhow tactical actions steps for coupling quality with customers or customers including three Vs to Satisfactory quality scene: Value segment, Value proposition, and Value network recovering satisfaction are as follows (Curran, et al, 1994; Fegh-hi farahmand, 2004, 358; Fegh-hi farahmand, 2005, 187; Nayak, et al, 1994, 47; North, et al, 1997, 187):

- 1) Top manager support: An organization's total quality efforts must begin at the very top and begin with the board of directors (Olivero, et al, 1997, 68; Senge, 1990, 196; Perry, 2001, 66).
- 2) Action plan: An action plan based on the survey feedback should then be formulated by the top management and communicated at every board meeting.
- 3) Vision: Develop a vision the organization does not have one already. The key to the initial adoption of quality is continuous communication of the vision within a comprehensive communication plan.
- 4) Quality improvements: Senior managers need coaching as the new theorists in coaching argue; coaching empowers individuals to achieve their inherent potential.
- 5) Quality circles: Employees, shareholders and customers, suppliers and competitors have a stake and essential ingredient for success is senior quality circles, which provides leadership in quality and stimulates cultural change.
- 6) Responsibility: The responsibilities accept of a senior quality committee can include (Fegh-hi farahmand, 2004, 398): establishing strategic quality goals, allocating resources, sanctioning quality improvement teams, reviewing key indicators of quality, estimating the cost of poor quality, ensuring adequate training of employees and recognizing and rewarding individual and team efforts.

For this reason, there is a need to re-track fundamental management systems. Such concepts as investment valuation, ethical trading, stakeholder consultation, corporate social responsibility, value investment, preoccupy institutional investor communities.

In any case, the level of uncertainty is continuing to increase even as consumer prosperity overlaps into the new century, reacting against the undoubted brilliance of the recent industrial era. However, the mainly qualitative evidence available to date suggests that SP within organizations is an activity of a minority (Bolton, et al, 2000, 88; Fegh-hi farahmand, 2002, 254). There may be a number of reasons for the lack of SP. Historically the typical schematized structure has tended not to have pursued higher levels of education level or to take formal satisfactory quality scene training. Hence there are two possible reasons why schematized structure tend not to plan (Chell, 1991, et al, 167; Barkham, et al, 1996, 27) that they are emotionally unsuited to it. They think and act intuitively and they are simply unaware of the various tools which would enable them to plan systematically.

A further constraint, likely to restrict satisfactory quality scene relationship by schematized structure, is that they may not have sufficient financial information to prepare a formal plan. A lack of formal satisfactory quality scene relationship planning may also relate to the fact that small organizations are just too busy surviving to take time out to plan ahead whilst others might argue the environment (Ledoux, 1993, 215; Ledoux, 1994, 15). A lack of formal satisfactory

quality scene relationship among organizations does not necessarily mean that organization is badly managed. It does, however, suggest that schematized structure miss out on the opportunity to consider the overall direction of the satisfactory quality scene and management decisions may be made on the basis of poor information (Curran, et al, 1994, 39; Fegh-hi farahmand, 2009, 102; Stutely, 2002, 43; Watts & et al, 2003, p 197).

3. SCHEMATIZED STRUCTURE

Organizational relationship management systems were both outcome focused and financially focused and were neither multidimensional nor strategic.

The nature of the schematized structure is seen as critical in other aspects (Nayak et al, 1994, 425; Fisher, 2002, 89) of the activities of organizations. A selection of the schematized structure' characteristics is the potential to influence an owner manager's propensity to undertake organizational relationship management. Predictions of the direction in which the variables (Fegh-hi Farahmand, 2002, 345; Smith, 1967, 145) will operate are inevitably problematic as there is little prior work on the determinants of organizational relationship management upon which we can draw (Smith, 1967, 25; Curran, et al, 1994; Fegh-hi farahmand, 2005, 37; Kuratko & et al, 2004, 64):

- 1) Satisfactory quality scene relationship ability: This variable has been identified as important in a number of studies.
- 2) Satisfactory quality scene relationship experience: It may be strongly linked to ability and it could be argued that it might work in two ways. A long number of years running an organization as an schematized structure might increase a propensity to plan future directions for the satisfactory quality scene or indeed, once the initial phases had passed and funding secured planning might well be less of a priority.
- 3) Satisfactory quality scene relationship education level: In the context of organizational relationship management, this variable might seem reasonable to hypothesis that the more highly educated schematized structure will tend to be more aware of the desirability of organizational relationship management and thus, organization run by the better educated schematized structure might be more likely to have satisfactory quality scene plans.
- 4) Satisfactory quality scene relationship innovation: A distinction here may be drawn between those for whom the current organization is their first and serial founders.
- 5) Satisfactory quality scene relationship organizing: Organization founders are drawn either from operatives or from those with previous managerial experience.
- 6) Satisfactory quality scene relationship strategy: Here it might be argued that schematized structure moving into a new sector might be encouraged to plan rather more than those whose businesses were in sectors in which they had considerable prior experience.
- 7) Satisfactory quality scene relationship potential: This was introduced into the analysis as it might be expected that local schematized structure, who grew up in the geographical area under study, will tend to be introspective and less receptive to contemporary management practice.

The relationships between organizations and their localities have become an important research area and organization with links with local satisfactory quality scene institutions might be more likely to satisfactory quality scene plan. The argument here would be that mixing with local satisfactory quality scene leaders would increase awareness of the value of organizational relationship management. Conversely, mixing with other schematized structure of small organization might re-enforce towards the idea of organizational relationship management, especially where organizational relationship management was not seen as a key element of satisfactory quality scene activity.

4. SATISFACTORY QUALITY SCENE RELATIONSHIP MANAGEMENT

The capturing the wrong organizational customers information, unclear goals, inappropriate selection and use of technology, inability to integrate people and processes and use of misleading metrics or improper measurement approaches are the major barriers in implementing and managing organizational customers projects. The seven deadly sins for unsatisfactory satisfactory quality scene relationship management outcome are:

- Viewing the satisfactory quality scene relationship management initiative as a technology initiative;
- Lack of organizational customers vision;
- Insufficient appreciation of organizational customers' lifetime satisfies;
- Inadequate support from top management;
- Underestimating the importance of change management;
- Failing to re-engineer organization processes;

The satisfactory quality scene relationship management refers to the internal systematic approach systematically of the organization management and leadership to strive for organization successful excellence. The successful satisfactory quality scene relationship management referring to all those measures through which one creates and strengthens confidence and trust in outsiders, especially service receivers, towards the organization abilities and service. When the comprehensiveness of the satisfactory quality scene relationship management approach is being emphasized one also can use the concept satisfactory quality scene relationship management instead of satisfactory quality scene plan. In practice, however, the both mean the same.

The aim of satisfactory quality scene relationship management approach is to strive for the organization strategic and operational goals. Satisfactory quality scene relationship management is based on a special expertise for enhancing effectiveness and efficiency of organization management and leadership. Thus genuine realization of the satisfactory quality scene relationship management practices takes place in real organization activities both in the organization strategic leadership as well as in the operational realization of the organization services and targets.

The broad challenge for satisfactory quality scene relationship management is to enhance positive substance of organization brand through various means that are consistent both with respect to one another and aligned with the organization strategic course.

As a whole the main principles in organizations approach include the following:

- Focus on supporting the satisfactory quality scene relationship management strategic goals of the organization;
- Consistency of different satisfactory quality scene relationship measures in order to strengthen one another;
- Alignment of the whole strategically and operationally for centering on the key issues;
- Comprehensiveness and a scope which covers the entire corporation;
- Integrating satisfactory quality scene relationship management measures with organization processes.

Systematic approach instead of building separate systems such as quality systems satisfactory quality scene relationship management approach is well harmonized with the organization strategies. On that basis also the quality policy was defined. General intention and direction towards satisfactory quality scene relationship management is considered by the satisfactory quality scene policy statements:

- Always act so that the organizational customers what he or she needs;
- Improve activities and their results continually so that they will be better and more effective and efficient of satisfactory quality scene relationship management.

The goal of satisfactory quality scene relationship management, i.e. organization excellence, is reached through innovative management and leadership practices.

In order to realize satisfactory quality scene relationship management objectives in all parts of the organization and at all levels of organization and management, an organization-wide management structure, a leadership infrastructure framework has been defined. The framework model was originally created at organizations. This model covers all organization functions in a natural and flexible manner and covers the following four levels of the organization:

- 1) The organization level: where the general principles, the common insight, goals, shared tools, and practices concerning satisfactory quality scene relationship management are created, including how these principles are to be applied in practice on the basis of the organization requirements.
- 2) The strategic areas and unit's level: where decisions are made by the general manager of the organization unit and the other top organization leaders, and measures undertaken concerning the entire particular organization and especially the future competitiveness of the organization and management of the whole organization system are addressed. The organization system is composed of the interrelated operational organization processes. Very often in corporations there

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL of RESEARCH –GRANTHAALAYAH

A knowledge Repository

are different organization areas that may be at different development stages. All these need different strategic satisfactory quality scene relationship management approaches but they may operate within one corporate culture.

3) The operational individual organization processes level: where decisions and measures concerning daily management are made and undertaken, and services are realized in real time for organizational customer's needs.

4) The human and team's level: where the personal contribution of each member of the organization personnel including the top management is provided in natural working environments.

5. RESULTS

Schematized structure ranged in ability from low to high. Clearly, within this group, there is a sub set of growth oriented schematized structure whose propensity to undertake organizational relationship management might be contrasted with those who were content with their current level of satisfactory quality scene. The latter may well belong to that group of schematized structure often characterized as running lifestyle organization. From this overview of the selected schematized structure' characteristics and the strategies of the sampled organization, it is now possible to explore the extent to which these differing characteristics and strategies influence whether or not an organization engages in organizational relationship management.

6. CONCLUSION

Many of organizations have sustained their satisfactory quality scene relationship management systems focus over time, although these investments may or may not be considered part of a long-term satisfactory quality scene relationship management strategy. The scope, size, complexity and duration of the satisfactory quality scene relationship management projects seem to vary quite significantly across organizations. Poor planning, lack of clear objectives and not recognizing the need for organization change are the key reasons for satisfactory quality scene relationship failures.

The most recent satisfactory quality scene relationship management programs, for example some have clearly benefited from previous satisfactory quality scene relationship management systems experience of suppliers, including considerably reduced implementation times and lower risk levels for comparable size programs. All these organizations had very different levels of success. Their success was determined mainly by the relationship between the complexity of the system and the speed and phasing of its development and roll out. A satisfactory quality scene relationship management system is not just service receiver interface software. Organizations believe that successful measurement frameworks should be multidimensional. Unfortunately, the early attempts at successful measurement frameworks were too financially oriented and did not provide strategic vision. The main focus is on the role of schematized structure characteristics in influencing the propensity for organizational relationship management. The interdisciplinary conceptual model will provide guidance to schematized structure in developing contextually

relevant method measures. The model provides schematized structure with specific benefits such as:

- Measures to satisfactory quality scene relationship management with strategically aligned framework for clearer logic behind satisfactory quality scene relationship management actions.
- Successful measure portfolio that discriminates between satisfactory quality scene relationship management efficiency and effectiveness successful measures in order to avoid suboptimal successful.
- Set of satisfactory quality scene relationship management guidelines to ensure method synergies are achieved in the targeting of high and low organizational customers lifetime satisfy segments with matching method costs and method response to organizational customers satisfy.

Schematized structure have too many successful measures, and a simplified set with fewer yet more important metrics would lead to superior successful. Successful schematized structures are hindered by too many low-level measures. Ideal successful schematized structure must include measures which are strategically relevant as well as measures which address both efficiency and effectiveness of satisfactory quality scene relationship management. For schematized structure, the area of organizational relationship method successful measurement is an area that represents a significant opportunity for satisfactory quality scene relationship management investment and satisfactory quality scene plan management attention. In order to understand whether the schematized structure is performing or not, we need to ensure that the schematized structure is appropriate for each satisfactory quality scene strategy. In response to this research gap, this paper investigates whether schematized structure should differ according to satisfactory quality scene strategy.

7. REFERENCES

- [1] Bolton, B and Thompson J (2000), *Entrepreneurs, Talent, Temperament and Technique*. London, Butterworth Heinemann, pp 65-97.
- [2] Bridge, S. O'Neill, K and Cromie S (1998), *Understanding Enterprise, Entrepreneurship & small Business*. London, Macmillan Business, p 124.
- [3] Brown, S. & Eisenhardt, K. (1998), *Competing on the Edge*, Harvard Business School Press, pp68-91.
- [4] Burns, P. (2001), *Entrepreneurship and small Business*. Basingstoke, Palgrave. Pp 34-74.
- [5] Chakravarthy, B. S. (1986) 'Measuring strategic successful', *Strategic Management Journal*, Vol. 7, No. 5, pp. 437-458.
- [6] Chell, E. (2001), *Entrepreneurship: Globalization, Innovation and Development*, London, Thomson Learning, p67.
- [7] Chell, E. Haworth, J. and Brearley, S. A. (1991), *The Entrepreneurial Personality*, London, Rutledge, p 167.

- [8] Collins, F., Holzmann, O. and Mendoza, R. (1997) 'Strategy, budgeting, and crisis in Latin America', *Accounting and Society*, Vol. 22, No. 7, pp. 669–689.
- [9] Curran, J. and Blackburn, R. (1994), *Business planning and Local Economic Networks*, London, Paul Chapman, pp 31-49.
- [10] Day, G. (2000) 'Capabilities for forging Customer relationships', Report No. 00–118, Satisfactory quality scene Science Institute, Cambridge, MA.
- [11] Deakin, D. & Freel, M. (2003), *Entrepreneurship and Business planning*, London, McGraw Hill, pp 302-412.
- [12] Dobni, B., Dobni, D. and Luffman, G. (2001) 'Behavioural approaches to satisfactory quality scene strategy implementation', *Satisfactory quality scene Intelligence & Planning*, Vol. 19, No. 6, pp. 400–408.
- [13] Eccles, R. G. (1991) 'The successful measurement manifesto', *Harvard Business Review*, Vol. 69, No. 1, pp. 131–137.
- [14] Erffmeyer, R. C. and Johnson, D. A. (2001) 'An exploratory study of sales force automation practices: Expectations and realities', *Journal of Personal Selling and Sales Management*, Vol. 21, No. 2, pp. 167–175.
- [15] Fegh-hi Farahmand, Nasser (2001), *Executive Management Process*, Islamic Azad University, Tabriz Branch, Iran, pp 99-113.
- [16] Fegh-hi Farahmand, Nasser (2003), *Permanent Management of Organization*, First edition, Frouzesh Publication, Tabriz, Iran, pp 70-83.
- [17] Fegh-hi Farahmand, Nasser (2003), *Strategic Structure of Organization Management Process*, Forth edition, Islamic Azad University, Tabriz Branch, Iran, pp 41-125.
- [18] Fegh-hi Farahmand, Nasser (2005), *Strategic Management of Organization*, First edition, Frouzesh Publication, Tabriz, Iran, pp 85-149.
- [19] Fegh-hi Farahmand, Nasser (2009), *Organization Strategic Plan compilation*, First edition, Frouzesh Publication, Tabriz, Iran, pp 74-314.
- [20] Fegh-hi farahmand, Nasser (2011), *Active and Dynamic Management of Organization*, Second edition, Frouzesh Publication, Tabriz, Iran, pp 87-90.
- [21] Fegh-hi Farahmand, Nasser (2011a), *Technology Management of Organization*, Second edition, Frouzesh Publication, Tabriz, Iran, pp 11-18.
- [22] Fiegenger, M. K. (1994) 'Matching organization-level strategic controls to strategy: Impact on control system effectiveness', *Journal of Applied organization Research*, Vol. 10, No. 1, pp. 25–34.
- [23] Fisher, A. (2002), *Annie weighs in on executive coaching and untruths on resumes*, *Fortune Magazine*, 13 May, o 89.
- [24] Franco, M. and Bourne, M. (2003) 'Factors that play a role in 'managing through measures'', *Management Decision*, Vol. 41, No. 8, pp. 698–710.
- [25] Gifford, D (1997), *The value of going green*, *Harvard Business Review*, 75/5.

- [26] Goleman, D (1996), *Emotional Intelligence*, London, Bloomsbury, p58.
- [27] Goleman, D., Boyatzis, R. & McKee, A. (2002), *The New Leaders*, London, Little, Brown, p 78-199.
- [28] Govindarajan, V. and Fisher, J. (1990) 'Strategy, control systems, and resource sharing: Effects on organization-unit successful', *Academy of Management Journal*, Vol. 33, No. 2, pp. 259–285.
- [29] Gresov, C. and Drazin, R. (1997) 'Equifinality: Functional equivalence in organization design', *Academy of Management Review*, Vol. 22, No. 2, pp. 403–428.
- [30] Hamel, G. (2001), *Leading the Revolution*, Boston, Harvard Business School Press, p89.
- [31] Henningsen, C (2002), *Investing as if the world really mattered*, *Corporate Environmental Strategy*, 9 /2, pp 22-39.
- [32] Hunt, S. D. and Lambe, J. (2000) 'Satisfactory quality scene's contributions to organization strategy; Market orientation, relationship satisfactory quality scene, and resource-advantage theory', *International Journal of Management Reviews*, Vol. 2, No. 1, pp. 17–34.
- [33] J Anttila (2001): "Effective quality communication." *St. Petersburg: Stocholm School of Economics*
- [34] J Anttila (2002): "Product quality in software organization connection". *Conference on software quality connection, Helsinki*
- [35] J Anttila (2002): "Using Malcolm Baldrige model for organization excellence", *Institute of Directors, New Delhi*
- [36] J Anttila, J Vakkuri (2000): "Good Better Best", *Sonera Corporation, Helsinki*
- [37] Jain, R., Jain, S. and Dhar, U. (2007) 'CUREL: A scale for measuring service receiver relationship management effectiveness in service sector', *Journal of Services Research*, Vol. 7, No. 1, pp. 37–58.
- [38] Jaworski, B. J. and Kohli, A. K. (1991) 'Market orientation', *Journal of Satisfactory quality scene*, Vol. 57, No. 3, pp. 53–70.
- [39] Jeuland, A. P. and Shugan, S. M. (1983) 'Managing method profits', *Satisfactory quality scene Science*, Vol. 2, No. 3, pp. 239–272.
- [40] Johnson, Steven (2001), *The connected lives of ants, brains, cities and software*, Penguin, pp 44-63.
- [41] *Journal of Database Satisfactory quality scene & Customer Strategy Management* (2008) 15, 68–78. doi:10.1057/dbm.2008.5; published online 9 June 2008
- [42] Kale, S. H. (2004) 'SRRM failure and the seven deadly sins', *Satisfactory quality scene Management*, Vol. 13 (September/October), pp. 42–46.
- [43] Kaplan, R. S. and Norton, D. P. (1996) 'Using the balanced scorecard as a strategic management system', *Harvard Business Review*, Vol. 74, No. 1, pp. 75–85.
- [44] Kirby, D. A. (2003), *Entrepreneurship*, Maidenhead, McGraw Hill, p 82

- [45] Kumar, K. and Subramanian, R. (1997/1998) 'Porter's strategic types: Differences in internal processes and their impact on successful', *Journal of Applied organization Research*, Vol. 14, No. 1, pp. 107–124.
- [46] Kuratko D F and Hodgetts R M (2004), *Entrepreneurship: Theory, Practice* Mason, Ohio, Thomson South Western, p64.
- [47] Larson, P. D. (1991) 'Product quality, total costs and the integration of the utility-producing functions unpublished PhD dissertation University of Oklahoma.
- [48] Larson, P. D. and Lusch, R. F. (1992) 'Functional integration in satisfactory quality scene methods: A determinant of product quality and total cost', *Journal of Satisfactory quality scene Methods*, Vol. 2, No. 1, pp. 1–28.
- [49] Lassar, W. M. and Kerr, J. L. (1996) 'Strategy and control in supplier-distributor relationships: An agency perspective', *Strategic Management Journal*, Vol. 17, No. 8, pp. 613–632.
- [50] Lebas, M. and Euske, K. (2002) 'Delineation of successful', in: Neely, A. (Ed.) 'Performance measurement: Theory and practice', Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, UK, pp. 65–79.
- [51] Ledoux, JE (1993), *Emotional memory systems in the brain. Scene and Brain Research*, v 58, p 112-215.
- [52] Lewis, M. C. and Lambert, D. M. (1991) 'A model of method member successful, dependence, and satisfaction', *Journal of Retailing*, Vol. 67, No. 2, pp. 205–225.
- [53] Lubieniecki, E. C. and Desrocher, N. J. (2003) 'The case for simple comparison: A simple successful scorecard for effectiveness and efficiency', *Journal of Corporate Real Estate*, Vol. 6, No. 1, pp. 39–52.
- [54] Maselli, J. (2001) 'People problems', *InformationWeek*, 9 July, pp.35–42.
- [55] Mason, C and Stark, M. (2004), *What do investors look for Business Plan*, *International small Business Journal*, 22, p3.
- [56] McGovern, J., Lindemann, M., Vergara, M., Murphy, S, Barker, MA & Warrenfeltz, R. (2001), *Maximizing the impact of executive coaching: Sceneal change, organisational outcomes, and return on investment*. www.mentors.ca/coachingnews.html.
- [57] Merlin Stone, 1 Broadmead Close, Hampton, TW12 3RT, UK.
- [58] Michael J. Valos, Faculty of organization and Law Bowater School of Management & Satisfactory quality scene Deakin University, 221 Burwood Highway Burwood Vic. 3125 Australia.
- [59] Miles, R. E. and Snow, C. C. (1978) 'Organisational strategy, structure, and process', McGraw-Hill, New York.
- [60] Minnow, N (1996), *Downsizing corporate responsibility. Public Relations Strategy* 2, vol. 3, p5.
- [61] Mintzberg, H. (1994), *The rise and fall of Strategic Planning*, Prentice Hall International, p81-109.

- [62] Mintzberg, H., Alstrand, B. & Lample, J. (1998), *Strategy Safari*. The Free Press, pp 23-67.
- [63] Moedritshcher, G. and Mussnig, W. (2005) 'Evaluating the long term benefit of SRRM-systems: A cost-oriented approach', *International Journal of Innovation and Technology Management*, Vol. 2, No. 4, pp. 367–389.
- [64] Naffziger, D. Kuratko, D. (1991), *An Investigation into the Planning In small Business*, *Journal of Business and Entrepreneurship*, Fall, p 21.
- [65] Najmi, M., Rigas, J. and Fan, I. -S. (2005) 'A framework to review successful measurement systems', *organization Process Management Journal*, Vol. 11, No. 2, pp. 109–122
- [66] Nayak, A and Greenfield, S. (1994), *The Use Of Management Accounting Information, Finance and the organizations*, London, Rutledge, p47.
- [67] Schwenk, C. R. and Shrader, C. B. (1993), *Effects Of Formal Strategic Planning, Entrepreneurship: Theory and Practice*, p17.
- [68] Senge P, Roberts C and Ross B. Kleiner A (1995): "The Fifth Discipline Fieldbook", Nicholas Brealey Publishing Limited, London
- [69] Senge, P. M. (1990) 'The leader's new work. Building learning organizations', *Sloan Management Review*, Vol. 32, pp. 7–24.
- [70] Simons, R. (1987) 'Accounting control systems and organization strategy: An empirical analysis', *Accounting organizations and Society*, Vol. 12, No. 4, pp. 357–374.
- [71] Sirivastava, R. K., Shervani, T. A. and Fahey, L. (1999) 'Satisfactory quality scene, organization process, and shareholder satisfy: An organizationally embedded view of satisfactory quality scene activities and the discipline of satisfactory quality scene', *Journal of Satisfactory quality scene*, Vol. 63, No. 4, pp. 168–179
- [72] Slater, S. F. and Narver, J. C. (1995) 'Market orientation and the learning organization', *Journal of Satisfactory quality scene*, Vol. 59, No. 3, pp. 63–74.
- [73] Smith, N. R. (1967), *The Entrepreneur and His Organization*, University of Michigan: Bureau of Business and Economic Research, pp 112-184.
- [74] Speier, C. and Venkatesh, V. (2002) 'The hidden minefields in the adoption of sales force automation technologies', *Journal of Satisfactory quality scene*, Vol. 66, No. 3, pp. 98–112.
- [75] Stacey, R. D. (2000), *Strategic Management and Organisational Dynamics*, Prentice Hall, p 23-42.
- [76] Steele, R. S. (1977), *Power motivation, activation and inspirational speeches*. *Journal of Personality*, 45, pp 28-68.